

THE IMPACT OF INDIAN FOOD INFLATION ON FOOD SECURITY IN BANGLADESH 2022

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Abstract

Food inflation in India, caused by climate change, heat waves, and droughts, has significantly impacted Bangladesh's food security. This study examines the impact of India's food inflation on Bangladesh, using food security and food inflation theories. The findings reveal that rising food prices in India directly affect Bangladesh's food import prices, threatening its welfare and health. To improve food security, Bangladesh should diversify food sources, strengthen distribution systems, and support sustainable food production. Regional and international cooperation is crucial to address the impact of food inflation on Bangladesh's food security. The study concludes that effective policies and cooperation between countries are essential for addressing this issue.

Keywords: Inflation, Food Security, India Bangladesh Bilateral Relationship

Introduction

Base on World Food and Agriculture Organization (WFAO), some of the main dimensions written in the definition of food security is including food availability, physical and economic accessibility to food, and food sustainability and stability (Syahyuti et al., 2016). Food security is important for all countries as it is directly related to the survival and population of the world (Suharyanto, 2011). Food is also a basic need of living beings and of the human rights, food security is a condition of food fulfillment from the state to individuals which is reflected in the availability of adequate food both in quantity and nutrition and does not conflict with religion, beliefs, and culture of the community so that it is related to health and sustainable productivity (Ariningsih et al., 2008).

The Causes of food inflation in India in 2022 is uncertain climate conditions, when drought happened (BBC, 2023). Climate change has major influence on India's food inflation, with prolonged heat waves and droughts as one of the contributing factors to the failure of India's domestic agriculture. Food inflation is also aggravated by several other factors including heatwaves and climatic factors (CNBC Indonesia, 2023) which will lead to domestic crop failure in 2022. comparatively low demand elasticity for food as a result of natural disasters reducing output. Furthermore the rice supply in India decision to of limited rice exports. India's decision to limit rice exports influences the country's domestic food needs.

In 2022, Bangladesh is experienced food crisis which caused by various factors faced by domestic Bangladeshis, including climate disruption, and domestic conflict. The Global Report on the Food Crisis (GRFC) 2023, revealed that there were approximately 51 million Bangladeshis facing acute food insecurity in 2022 (Ouko & Odiwuor, 2023). This is not because domestic conflicts that have reduced people's ability to earn income and limited food accessibility, but due to the failure of domestic food production due to climate change and lack of rainfall causing domestic crop failures. The food crisis in Bangladesh not only occur in 2022, but based on historical data, there have been five major floods in the last 50 years that have resulted in food inflation. Bangladesh's food crisis is directly influenced by natural disasters that damaged 30% of agricultural land, Bangladesh was also hit by a cyclone in 2007 that damaged nearly 2.5 million hectares and 1.87 million livestock died (Vermeulen et al., 2012).

The impact of inflation in India also affects countries that rely on imported food, one of the countries affected by Indian Inflation is Bangladesh. The impacts felt by Bangladesh is food security that the ban on rice exports by India in July 2023 affect food availability in Bangladesh, then the increase in commodity prices, Indian inflation caused an increase in commodity prices including rice by 11.51%, and an increase in food

prices. India's exports to Bangladesh reached US\$13.83 Billion in 2022, according to the UN COMTRADE database on international trade. India exports to Bangladesh - data, historical charts and statistics - last updated in 2023. This year, India exported grains, cereals and rice which are staple food items with a total value of USD 1.57 billion.

The explanation that has been presented above, can be seen regarding the phenomenon of inflation and food security which is now an ongoing issue and needs to be discussed. So that the issue of inflation and food security is one of the authors' interests to be used as a research, because starting from basic foodstuffs can have a big impact, therefore researchers conducted a study entitled "**The impact of Indian food inflation on food security in Bangladesh 2022**".

Methodology

This research discussed "The impact of Indian food inflation on food security in Bangladesh 2022". The research methodology used in this study was qualitative, and the books, journal, and articles that served as the research sources were all pertinent to the study's topic. While the approach in this study was qualitative descriptive method. By accurately portraying reality with words that are generated based on pertinent data analysis collection methodologies and collected from scientific scenarios, qualitative research was a scientific methodology that expresses particular social situations. In this method, the researcher provided an overview of the problem topic using relevant concepts or theories as written in the previous subchapter.

Results and Discussion

Theoretical Framework

The first theory that will be used for this research is Food Security Theory, Food Security Theory is one of the theories contained in International Relations, this theory discusses various aspects related to security, in International Relations this theory discusses food supply and also the availability of global foodstuffs and cooperation between countries to ensure global food availability. Food security according to FAO in the World Food Conference in 1996 stated that food security is a condition where everyone can have physical and economic access to sufficient, safe, and nutritious food to meet their food and nutrition needs (Boliko, 2019).

Food security also includes external factors such as climate change, conflicts between countries, economic crises that affect production and access to food. Food security theory can also be used as a political tool by powerful countries to gain an advantage in the international food trade which causes inequality in food access between global countries.(Prince, 2015) There are also several opinions on food security according to international relations scholars, including criticism of global market dependence, global security and conflict linkages, international cooperation, linkages to global issues and political and national security aspects (Erwandari, 2017).

The theory of food inflation in international relations examines the consequences of sustained increases in food prices globally. Food inflation can originate from both demand-side factors (demand pull inflation) and supply-side factors (cost push inflation). Rising food prices can reduce people's purchasing power, especially the more economically vulnerable groups, and can destabilize a country's economy. Regulating food inflation through supply, distribution and pricing policies is crucial in international relations.

In the Indonesian context, the Central Bureau of Statistics (BPS) publishes inflation figures by category, including food inflation (BPS, 2022). Efforts to control food inflation are carried out through flagship initiatives

and inter-agency cooperation, such as the National Movement for Food Inflation Control (GNPIP) involving Bank Indonesia and relevant ministries. Therefore, the theory of food inflation in international relations includes the study of the impact of rising food prices, control tactics, and inter-agency cooperation to uphold economic stability and public welfare.

Description of the Object of Research Inflation in India

Bangladesh's Economy and Food Production

There are several reasons that Bangladesh is categorized as a poor country located in Asia, some of the factors are slow economic growth, relatively low economic growth in the banking sector and industrial sector. Bangladesh's demographic transition has a fast-growing population that requires basic services such as health care, nursing care, infrastructure and education (CEIC, 2021). However, the rapid population growth rate, coupled with the poverty factor, adds to the poverty factor of the country. Bangladesh's relatively small per capita economic growth also makes Bangladesh one of the poorest countries in Asia. Bangladesh's trade and industrial growth is still in the developing phase, so many sectors still have shortcomings in terms of investors and innovation, to achieve better growth targets. The relatively low level of investment in Bangladesh, so reforms in government policies are needed to create a new attraction for investors who want to invest in Bangladesh (Siakap Keli, 2022).

Tabel 1. Bangladesh's Food Production Data in 2022

Bangladesh Food Production Data 2022				
No	Product	Area	Production	Productivity
1	Paddy	11,8 million hectares	37,5 million tons	18 tons/ha
2	Wheat	0,75 million ha	1,5 million tons	2 tons/ha
3	Corn	0,5 million ha	0,8 million tons	1,6 tons/ha
4	Sugarcane	0,2 million ha	2,2 million tons	11 tons/ha
5	Potato	0,18 million ha	1,8 million tons	10 tons/ha
6	Cassava	0,15 million ha	2,5 million tons	16,7 tons/ha

Source: Bangladesh Agriculture Ministry)(Kementrian Agriculture Bangladesh - Yahoo Search Results, 2022)

Although Bangladesh has been able to produce as much food as the table above, and Bangladesh has also been able to implement Food Sufficiency, but Bangladesh's domestic food production is still unable to meet 100% of Bangladesh's food needs, this is due to the high rate of rapid population growth in Bangladesh, as well as the lack of modern technology in agriculture in Bangladesh adding to the limited factor of food production in Bangladesh, which then has an impact on the availability of food in Bangladesh, so Bangladesh still needs additional food supplies to meet basic domestic food needs.

Bangladesh also runs a food self-sufficiency program for domestic food needs, the definition of food self-sufficiency is the ability of a country

to meet domestic food needs without having to rely on food imports from other countries (Santoso, 2003). The definition of food self-sufficiency is not only about the amount of production that a country can produce, but also includes the availability of food, accessibility, which means that people are able to buy food and food price stability that does not experience price inflation. Food self-sufficiency itself aims to improve national food security, national food security is a condition when all people are able to have access to safe, nutritious and sustainable food, without having to fear hunger or food crises. Improving the welfare of farmers, food self-sufficiency is also able to help lift the economy of farmers to be more stable with the selling price of crops that increase. Reducing dependence on imports, food self-sufficiency can help reduce a country's dependence on food imports from other countries, which are vulnerable to fluctuations in global crop prices (Badan Ketahanan Pangan Kementerian Pertanian Republik Indonesia, 2022).

Failure Factors and Bangladesh Food Insecurity

Food insecurity is a condition when a country is unable to provide sufficient food access for its people, resulting in food scarcity, difficulty in accessing safe and nutritious food for its people. There are many factors that affect Bangladesh's domestic agricultural production, these factors not only affect the domestic agricultural production sector, but these factors also affect Bangladesh's food self-sufficiency sector to meet domestic food needs, even these factors also affect Bangladesh's economic growth, these factors include:

1. Limited land and water, this limitation is a very influential factor in the agricultural production sector, where Bangladesh is very dependent on rainfall as well as Bangladesh does not have enough fertile land to grow various types of food-producing plants.

2. Natural disasters are the second most important factor in this sector, because Bangladesh has seasonal disasters that often occur every year, such as floods, storms and prolonged droughts, this worsens Bangladesh's domestic food production, which Bangladesh relies heavily on water needs for domestic agricultural irrigation with proper rainfall, but if there is a prolonged drought, then Bangladesh's domestic agriculture will experience crop failure due to lack of water for domestic agricultural irrigation.
3. Economic inequality, this also has an impact on food production and even Bangladesh's food security, because landowners can easily access their food resources, but not the farm laborers who work for food production. This is what makes the people of Bangladesh have a barrier between the rich and the poor in gaining access to proper food.
4. Dependence on a single crop, Bangladesh is currently dependent on only a few crops, the crop that Bangladesh depends on is rice, which affects Bangladesh's agricultural production and food production.
5. Lack of agricultural technology, this also affects the productivity of Bangladesh's agricultural production, because Bangladesh is still using traditional tools for agricultural activities that affect the efficiency of domestic agricultural productivity. Poverty, poverty is still something that affects many factors in Bangladesh, including the improvement of its economy, because of poverty, many Bangladeshis find it difficult to get access to food because of the inability of people to buy food (Barokatuminalloh, 2023).

The above are some of the main factors that cause crop failures in Bangladesh, domestic crop failures cause several major things to the people of Bangladesh, especially in the food sector, crop failures have an impact

on domestic food shortages, food shortages caused by domestic crop failures greatly impact food shortages, especially in rural areas of Bangladesh which cause malnutrition as well as hunger, especially for women and children.

Bangladesh Food Security Relevance to Indian Food Inflation

Bangladesh and India also have similarities in geography and nature, where both countries are located in South Asia, both countries have a fairly wide lowland and have rivers that cross the two countries, the climate of Bangladesh and India also has similarities, namely a tropical climate with relatively little rainfall, even the two countries have the same threat of natural disasters, where both countries are prone to natural disasters such as drought due to prolonged drought, floods, hurricanes and earthquakes (Hennida, 2012). The economic growth and development of Bangladesh and India also have several factors in common, Agriculture is a sector that has an important role for the economic growth of Bangladesh and India, the main crop cultivated in both countries is rice. The development of India and Bangladesh continues to be improved by the governments of the two countries, which aims to improve the standard of living of the people of the two countries, the construction of public facilities such as schools, health centers to road infrastructure continues to be improved (Todaro & Smith, 2006).

Food inflation in India has been a significant problem in recent years. India's food inflation rate has been high, averaging more than 9% between 2006 and 2013, almost double the previous inflation rate. These high inflation rates have a significant impact on people's well-being, especially for those living in rural areas and on low incomes, where a large portion of their income is used to buy food.

Food security in Bangladesh poses a major challenge, especially in rural areas. Several factors affect food security in the country including

geography, economic conditions and the impact of climate change. One of the main problems faced is the high level of chronic food insecurity, which is experienced by about 21% of the total population. Rangpur district in northern Bangladesh recorded the highest proportion of people experiencing chronic food insecurity, followed by Mymensingh and Barishal divisions. This shows that food security is still a major focus that needs to be taken seriously in Bangladesh. One of the proposed strategies to improve food security in the country is through crop diversification. Crop diversification has the potential to increase farmers' incomes, create jobs, reduce poverty levels, and maintain the sustainability of land and water resources that are essential to address the food crisis in developing countries. Thus, efforts to improve food security in Bangladesh require a holistic approach, which includes the promotion of sustainable agriculture, crop diversification and improved access to sufficient, safe and nutritious food resources for all sections of society (Nahar et al., 2024).

Bilateral cooperation between Bangladesh and India is reflected in the relationships and cooperative efforts established between the two countries in various fields, such as: Political: mainly to participate in international forums, facilitate the formulation of national policies, and strengthen diplomatic relations. Economic: Increasing trade and investment, building cooperative infrastructure, and reducing unemployment. Combating terrorism and transnational crime, holding joint military exercises, and disseminating intelligence information. Social and Religious: Strengthen religious programs, enhance interfaith harmony, and increase interfaith cooperation. Environment: Accommodating climate change, coping with natural disasters, and conserving natural resources. Bilateral cooperation objectives: Enhance inter-family relations and mutual understanding. Capitalize on shared potential to achieve economic maturity. Recognize common challenges such as terrorism and climate change. Enhance resilience and stability in Southeast Asia (Kumar, 2020).

The relationship between food inflation in India and food security in Bangladesh can be complex and intertwined due to various factors that affect both. One is the trade relationship between the two countries, where Bangladesh imports a large amount of food from India. If there is food inflation in India, it may lead to an increase in the price of imported food commodities in Bangladesh, which in turn will affect the availability and affordability of food for its population. In addition, food inflation in India could also have an impact on food prices globally, indirectly affecting food prices in Bangladesh. Rising food prices can increase food insecurity for vulnerable populations in Bangladesh. In response to this situation, the government of Bangladesh may need to take measures to mitigate the impact of food inflation, such as increasing domestic production, improving the food distribution system, and implementing price control mechanisms to ensure food security for its citizens.

The Impact of Indian Food Inflation on Bangladesh Food Security

Analysis of The Relations Between Food Inflation and Food Security

Food inflation is related to the changing price changes and shrinking food supplies, and resulted significant economic downturn, especially for consumers who are hesitant to purchase bananas. Various factors can cause inflation, including the effects of the "cost push" theory of inflation in response to rising production costs, rising energy prices, government prices, and the relatively elastic demand for bananas. One indicator that is often used to reduce food inflation is the Consumer Price Index (CPI), which tracks changes in the prices of goods and services purchased by the public. Food inflation will provide public welfare and a stable economy, which is often carefully monitored and managed by the government and monetary authorities (World Bank, 2024).

The inflation rate, which is the change of food prices, can affect macroeconomic stability and the purchasing power of the general public.

Contributors to the inflation rate can push up the prices of food commodities, due to high demand for foodstuffs and insufficient supply. This shows that food inflation can have a negative impact on food availability and people's purchasing power. On the other hand, the value of food commodities can be affected by food prices. Food inflation can affect local food production and domestic supply. First, food inflation can lead to higher food prices, which can affect people's purchasing power and reduce demand for local food products. Second, food inflation can cause an imbalance between demand and supply, which can negatively affect local and domestic food production. Third, food inflation may affect macroeconomic stability, which may affect investment and local food production. Therefore, it is crucial to monitor local food production and domestic supply.

Controlling food inflation has various benefits, including reducing dependence on food imports, optimizing food distribution and increasing local food production. In addition, cooperation between government agencies, businesses, regulators and the general public is essential to resolve issues related to food inflation and food security. Increased food price inflation can have a significant impact on domestic supply and local food production. One of the impacts is the increase in production costs, such as packaging, pesticides and raw materials, which can hamper fish production. In addition, food inflation can also lead to a shift in function from food crops to crops that have higher economic value, which can also hamper food production.

Food security, as defined by the World Food Conference of 1996, is the state in which every community can easily, safely, and nutritiously access food to meet their food and nutritional needs. There are several key components to the concept of food security that explain how a country can maintain its food security. This theory addresses food supply and availability both domestically and globally. The concept of food security also discusses external factors that affect food security, such as climate

change, conflicts between countries, economic crises that affect production and access to food, and government policies (Boliko, 2019).

Food production, distribution, and consumption are intimately linked to the ideas of food inflation and security. Food security is the capacity of a nation or region to sustainably supply the food demands of its population, whereas food inflation is the rise in food prices that has the potential to upset the macroeconomy and people's purchasing power. There is a complicated and frequently negative link between food inflation and food strength. Food inflation may have a detrimental effect on the general public's purchasing power and macroeconomic stability, which may then have an adverse effect on the availability and resilience of food. Reducing food inflation is a necessary step towards achieving food sustainability. Growing the amount of food produced locally is one of the actions that can be done (Pujayanti, 2016).

In a global context, food security and food inflation also have significant effects on developing countries. Countries with declining populations will experience food security and food inflation, which are more severe than developing countries. This is due to various factors, such as low investment in the petroleum sector, weather changes, and negative impacts on imported food. Therefore, efforts to improve food security and monitor food insecurity in developing countries are critical to achieve long-term development (Nainggolan, 2011).

Two concepts that are closely related and impact each other are food security and food inflation. Food inflation has the potential to negatively impact food availability and macroeconomic stability, which in turn can negatively impact food security. Furthermore, food security can contribute to food inflation by maintaining stable and rising food prices. Therefore, it is crucial to enhance food security and monitor food inflation to achieve sustainable development, especially in developing countries.

In the context of the relationship between food security and food inflation, there is a correlation between Bangladesh's food security and India's food inflation. Specifically, Bangladesh's food security is impacted by crop failures brought on by floods that have submerged 80% of the country's land, while India's food inflation is a result of domestic crop failures.

Islamic Food Security

Prophet Joseph's Food Policy, Planning for the Future to Overcome Famine The Prophet Joseph AS, for his intelligence, interpreted King Kiftir's dream about 7 years of fertile and 7 years of famine.

Which is written in Surah Yusuf verse 46 which reads:

يُوسُفُ أَيُّهَا الصِّدِّيقُ أَفْتِنَا فِي سَبْعِ بَقَرَاتٍ سِمَانٍ يَأْكُلُهُنَّ سَبْعٌ عِجَافٌ وَسَبْعِ سُنبُلَاتٍ خُضْرٍ
وَأُخْيِسِلَتْ لَعَلِّي أَرْجِعَ إِلَى النَّاسِ لَعَلَّهُمْ يَعْلَمُونَ

Meaning: (He said,) “O Joseph, a man of great trust, explain to us (the interpretation of the dream) of the seven fat cows that were eaten by the seven lean cows and the seven green stalks (of wheat) that (covered) the other seven dry stalks so that I may return to the people that they may know (QS.YUSUF - 46) (Saputra, 2023).

He was appointed food minister and formulated a food security strategy. First, the people were required to maximize the land to grow wheat during the 7-year fertile period, increasing the harvest by 2 times. The harvest was stored in granaries built throughout the region. Second, when the famine period arrived, food reserves were distributed in a planned manner to meet the needs of the people. This policy proved effective, the Egyptian people were spared from hunger, and the stability of the kingdom was maintained. The story of the Prophet Joseph is proof that the concept of food security that he initiated, with the principles of land optimization,

food logistics management, disaster mitigation, and early detection of weather anomalies, is still relevant today. Although in the modern era, technology has developed rapidly, the essence of the Prophet Joseph's policy, namely careful planning and measurable resource management, remains the key to realizing sustainable food security.

Analysis of Bangladesh and Indian Relations in Agriculture

As such, the relationship between Bangladesh and India exhibits complex and varied dynamics. Both have a number of factors driving their cooperation in various aspects, including trade, security, investment and diplomacy. By maintaining good relations and strengthening their cooperation, Bangladesh and India can achieve sustainable economic growth, enhance regional stability, and promote prosperity and security for both countries.

There are similarities between Bangladesh and India, these two countries in 2022 both have agricultural problems and food issues, which both countries face food price inflation and also face food insecurity, this problem is a big problem for both countries in 2022. Crop failure is an ongoing problem faced by Bangladesh and India, which is a major factor in India's food inflation and Bangladesh's food insecurity. Bangladesh's agricultural conditions in 2022 are facing a problematic period, Bangladesh's agricultural problems have an impact on domestic food production, agricultural problems facing Bangladesh include soil degradation, climate change, increasing population growth, ineffective management practices and unstable product prices (USDA, 2024).

In 2022 Bangladesh and India faced similar problems, both countries faced domestic crop failures, which impacted food inflation and food security of both countries, Bangladesh relied on India due to a number of factors including economic, security, political, and social aspects. India's presence as a major trading partner for Bangladesh is significant.

Bangladesh imports a wide range of goods from India, from consumer goods to industrial raw materials and machinery, while conversely, Bangladesh is also an important market for Indian products. Therefore, crop failures in India can have both direct and indirect impacts on the country's food security, and is a challenge that needs to be seriously addressed by the government and relevant parties (Villoria & Mghenyi, 2016). Food insecurity in India can be a contributing factor to food inflation. When food supply is insufficient to meet demand, food prices tend to rise due to high demand and limited supply. This situation may result from a decline in local food production due to crop failure or other factors. Food inflation can then cause difficulties for economically vulnerable groups of people to fulfill their food needs. Therefore, food insecurity can be one of the factors contributing to the problem of food inflation in India. To address food inflation caused by food insecurity, it is important for the Indian government to implement policies that support sustainable food production, improve food accessibility for people in need, and manage food markets efficiently to maintain price stability.

The impact of Indian inflation on Bangladesh

Bangladesh could be affected by food inflation in India as the country is a net importer of food. If food inflation in India leads to an increase in food prices globally, this could potentially affect Bangladesh's food import prices, which in turn will impact the country's domestic food security. Rising food prices can cause hardship for households in Bangladesh, especially for those who depend on food purchases for their daily needs. As an agricultural country with the majority of its population living in rural areas and dependent on the agricultural sector, fluctuations in global food prices can have a significant impact on the food security and economic well-being of households in Bangladesh. Therefore, changes in food prices, both in India and in the international market as a whole, can affect food security in Bangladesh (Headey & Martin, 2016).

Tabel 2. Impact of India's Inflation on Bangladesh's Food Security

Source: Processed data by researchers

Inflation indicators are caused by crop failure, climate problems, thus making prolonged drought that causes agriculture in India to experience a lack of water supply. Based on the explanation of the table above, it can be concluded that the inflation problem is caused by climate problems that affect Indian agriculture, so that India experienced crop failure in 2022 and triggered an increase in Indian food inflation. Bangladesh, which is one of the countries that imports food to fulfill domestic food supplies from India, is also affected by the inflation being faced by India, this has resulted in an increase in Bangladesh's domestic food prices due to an increase in food prices from India, then the decline in food access, and the increase in stunting and malnutrition, which is because the poor people of Bangladesh cannot afford to buy their food needs, let alone their nutritional needs.

There is a relationship between these conditions and food security, the relationship between the two conditions is that a country's food security can be influenced by this, a country will be safe from food insecurity if there are no problems in the agricultural sector of a country, problems in the agricultural sector affect the results of the quantity and quality of

production, if the quantity of production of a country decreases, it will affect domestic food security so that it threatens domestic food insecurity, so the state of a country's agriculture can affect the condition of domestic food security, so there is a relationship between agricultural conditions and food security.

Bangladesh's policy response to Indian food inflation.

Bangladesh has implemented a number of policies to maintain food security, including a National Food Policy that targets overall food security for the entire population. The main focus of this policy is to increase food production, expand access to food, and stabilize food prices. In addition, Bangladesh also implemented a National Nutrition Policy that addresses not only food security but also nutrition security. The policy highlights the importance of a balanced diet and adequate nutrient intake for all individuals, especially vulnerable groups such as children and pregnant women. Bangladesh also adopts a multisectoral approach in its efforts to address food security issues, involving various ministries, agencies and non-governmental organizations in policy making and implementation.

In addition, the country leverages social mobilization to advance food security initiatives, engaging various stakeholders including government agencies, non-governmental organizations and the general public. A number of programs and measures have been implemented by Bangladesh to improve the nutritional status of its population, such as promoting breastfeeding practices, micronutrient supplementation, and nutrition education. By implementing these policies and approaches, Bangladesh aims to increase food security, improve nutritional status, and ensure the well-being of its population (Karim, 2018). Food self-sufficiency is one example of a way for Bangladesh to get out of the Food Insecurity zone and out of the food inflation zone, although food self-sufficiency implemented by Bangladesh has not been fully successful in meeting

domestic food needs, so Bangladesh needs support by other countries to meet relatively large domestic food needs.

The efforts made by the Bangladeshi government are to increase domestic food production, this is done by Bangladesh to reduce food imports from other countries, as well as avoid food inflation, efforts made by Bangladesh in increasing food production to maintain domestic food needs and reduce food imports from other countries, this is included in the understanding of the concept of food security, which is written in the concept of food security, that large domestic production, is able to meet domestic food needs and no longer requires support for food imports from other countries to meet their food needs.

The next effort made by Bangladesh is to keep its people from being affected by food price inflation, the Bangladeshi government has implemented several policies for food trade and imports aimed at overcoming the increase in domestic food inflation, which the policy is carried out to adjust prices that can be reached by the people of Bangladesh, so that the people of Bangladesh are able to get food ingredients safely, easily and nutritiously, This is adopted from the explanation of the concept of food security, where the people of a country can be said to be safe, if all their food needs can be accessed easily, easy in the sense that it can be obtained easily both physically and economically, safe, safe which means that people can access food safely without hard work to get food because every community can access food evenly, and have access to food that is nutritious for the needs of the community.

Another effort made by Bangladesh in maintaining food security and food inflation is to run social assistance programs, this assistance is aimed at the lower middle class and vulnerable communities, this aims to equalize domestic food and reduce the level of hunger and domestic food insecurity. This program carries the mission of distributing free food aid to very vulnerable people, also this mission is very helpful for vulnerable people,

because even though Bangladesh has begun to be self-sufficient in food since a decade ago, hunger and food crises are still a topic that continues to exist, so the Bangladeshi government provides assistance by opening social assistance both from within the country and globally to help poor people to meet food needs.

In addressing food insecurity and food inflation, Bangladesh seeks to subsidize the people living in the middle and lower class, the subsidies they get from the government are in the form of food supplies, so that they can buy the food at a more affordable price so that they can meet their individual food needs. Providing subsidies to these communities is very helpful to them because it helps them meet their individual food needs. This is because these communities are in dire need of food, but they have difficulty gaining access to it because they live below the poverty line. This is part of the Food Insecurity variable where people cannot reach access to food easily due to economic factors.

To address these challenges, Bangladesh must consistently develop and implement holistic and long-term policies. Measures to increase production, protect consumers from price increases, provide social support to the lower classes, and ensure that food prices continue to be stabilized with the state of society. In addition, Bangladesh should continue to cooperate with other countries and international organizations to overcome obstacles and provide assistance in addressing the problem of food inflation and food insecurity in the future. In this way, Bangladesh can achieve greater success in ensuring food security for all its citizens.

The Impact of Government Policy on The Food Security of The Bangladesh's People.

Bangladesh has increased its investment in agricultural inputs, modern technologies, and agricultural infrastructure set up to improve the productivity, resilience, and efficiency of domestic agriculture. These

investments include the development of food varieties that are more resistant to drought and flooding, the use of practice-based agriculture, and improved access to agricultural services such as irrigation and crop pest control. However, even with the successes that have been achieved, there are still several issues that need to be addressed to improve food security in Bangladesh. Factors such as environmental fatigue, food insecurity and social distancing in relation to daily rainfall are still major concerns. Therefore, a comprehensive, holistic and sustainable approach is needed to formulate policies that can address current issues and ensure food security for all Bangladeshis.

Tabel 3. The Influence of Government Policies

Source: Processed data by researches

Bangladesh government policies in the domestic food production sector greatly affect the food security of the community, this policy has a positive effect on food production directly, because the Bangladesh government has provided many subsidies for food producers, such as providing fertilizer subsidies to farmers, promoting modern agricultural technology to proper production management, this has a positive effect on

domestic food availability as well as maintaining the stability of domestic food prices (Ananno et al., 2021).

The government of Bangladesh can influence food production through agricultural policies by providing incentives to farmers, promoting modern agricultural technologies, and allocating funds for agricultural infrastructure development. These measures can increase crop yields and food availability for local markets. In addition, policies that promote access to agricultural inputs such as seeds, fertilizers and irrigation can also help increase agricultural productivity, which in turn has a positive impact on food security. Apart from production, government policies also affect people's access to food. Government-run food subsidy programs or direct food assistance programs help ensure that vulnerable groups have access to adequate and nutritious food.

In addition, stable and transparent food pricing policies are also important to ensure food is affordable for all. Therefore, government policies in the agricultural sector and food policy as a whole have a significant impact on the food security of the people of Bangladesh. Through appropriate and effective policies, the government can play a role in increasing food production, ensuring food availability and accessibility for all citizens, and improving the country's overall food security.

In the implementation of its policies, Bangladesh has endeavored to implement the concept of food security, where every community is able to have safe access to achieve and access their food needs, both economically and nutritionally, this will continue to be maintained and maintained by Bangladesh, considering that the country is one of the most densely populated countries that requires sufficient food supply for its people.

Conclusion

Food inflation in India due to the effects of climate change as well as crop failures has a significant impact on Bangladesh's food security. Rising food prices in India have a direct impact on food import prices in Bangladesh, making it difficult for vulnerable groups to obtain food. This worsens the country's food security situation and threatens people's welfare and health. In addition, reduced food availability in Bangladesh affects children, increasing the risk of stunting and malnutrition. Disruptions to the food distribution system, such as speculation and hoarding of food by traders, also worsen the situation by causing food shortages in rural areas.

The Bangladeshi government has been forced to allocate more funds to subsidies and food aid programs, which could hamper other development and increase economic pressures. Rising food prices not only have economic impacts but also have social and political implications, with increased dissatisfaction with the government and the potential for protests and social unrest. Resolving this issue therefore requires inter-country cooperation and the implementation of comprehensive and effective policies. Efforts to improve food security in Bangladesh should include strategies to diversify food sources, strengthen distribution systems, and policies to support sustainable food production. In addition, regional and international cooperation will be important to address the impact of food inflation in India on food security in Bangladesh. Therefore, only a coordinated and comprehensive approach can effectively address the challenges of food inflation in India and safeguard the food security and well-being of the people of Bangladesh.

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